

Assessment of the Inhibitory Efficacy of Two Commonly Used Disinfectants (Ethanol and Phenol)

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 25 Aug 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Antibacterial Efficacy Disinfectants Bacteria Laboratory</p>	<p>Different kinds of disinfectants have been widely used in different research laboratories. In Nigeria, common laboratory disinfectants include alcohols like ethanol and also phenolic compounds. The antibacterial efficacy of two disinfectants (ethanol, phenol) was assessed in this study against isolate obtained from laboratory sites. Antibacterial activity test was carried out using agar plate diffusion method. Different concentrations of the disinfectants (1-5% for phenol, 50-70%, 85% and 99.7% for ethanol) were tested against the isolates. Isolates from laboratory sites used include <i>Escherichia hermannii</i>, <i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>, <i>Providencia stuartii</i>, <i>Leclercia adecarboxylata</i> and <i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>. Isolates were identified using standard microbiological techniques and Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time of flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectrometry. The outcome of the study showed phenol at a concentration of between 3-5% to have better inhibitory effects against the isolates compared to ethanol. The antimicrobial efficacy of disinfectants routinely supplied to the laboratory should be periodically assessed to ensure use at appropriate inhibitory concentration and proper control of infections.</p>

1. Introduction

A microorganism is a living thing that is too small to be seen with the naked eye. It includes bacteria, fungi, viruses and protozoa. Microorganisms are typically measured in micrometers (μm), with most bacteria measuring around 0.2 to 2.0 μm , while some viruses can be as small as 0.03 μm and protozoa can be 300 μm or larger (Pelczar and Pelczar, 1999). As a result of the ubiquity of microorganisms, infection control should be an integral part of the way of life in several areas of the environment (Curless et al., 2018). Laboratory-acquired and nosocomial infections have been previously reported as an important challenge globally and the characterization of microorganisms causing such infections is also important to prevent subsequent outbreaks (Jesumirhewe et al., 2022). Infection control has therefore been reported as an integral part of the culture in all hospitals. This involves rigorous cleaning and disinfection methods to ensure that the hospital environments are safe for the health workers and the patients (Guimaraes et al., 2000; Enitan et al., 2017). However, it should not be limited to the hospital environment (Rollins and Joseph, 2000).

There are various definitions of the process of disinfection and chemical disinfectants. Disinfection has been described as a control directed at eliminating harmful microorganisms. It usually involves the elimination of vegetative non-spore forming pathogens for example bacteria by using a disinfectant to treat an inanimate surfaces or substances (Bhatia and Icchpujani, 2008; Uzoечи et al., 2017). Generally disinfection reduces the level of microbial contamination unlike sterilization which eliminates nearly all recognized pathogenic microorganisms but not necessarily all microbial forms like bacterial spores (Enitan et al., 2017).

A disinfectant is one of the diverse groups of chemicals which reduce the number of microorganisms present (normally on an inanimate object) (Theraud et al., 2004; Uzoечи et al., 2017). Major types of disinfectants have been previously reported to include: Alcohols, Aldehydes, Oxidizing agents, Phenolics, Quaternary ammonium compounds, Silver, Copper alloy surfaces and Thymol-based disinfectants (OSHC, 2007; Uzoечи et al., 2017). Many studies have been done on comparison of disinfectant efficiency, and ethanol and bleach are believed to have immediate effect against most organisms (Carly et al., 2006). Bactericidal activity against key pathogens and time required to achieve lethal activity are the most important factors in disinfectant choice (Fraise, 1999). Safety in the use of effective disinfectant solutions with little/no damage to equipment and personnel is an important principle of disinfection.

While a consistent disinfection practice is important to reducing acquired infections from the environment, the need to ensure that potent disinfectants are used to achieve efficient disinfection cannot be underestimated. The activities of disinfectants depend on its consistent quality and efficacy which is of great importance in ensuring the quality of infection control (Piskin et al., 2011). Due to the differences in the isolates found in different environments and the continuous emergence and re-emergence of antibiotic-resistant isolates amongst other factors considered in the choice of disinfectants useful in infection control, the need to evaluate and reevaluate the efficacy of disinfectants been used in different environments from time to time is important. This study was carried out to evaluate the antibacterial efficacy of two disinfectants (ethanol and phenol) against laboratory isolates obtained from laboratory sites in the Department of Pharmaceutical microbiology, Igbinedion University Okada, Edo state Nigeria.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Sample collection

Two disinfectants Ethanol and Phenol were chosen for this study. They include some of the common products available in Nigerian markets for disinfection in hospitals, health centers and research laboratories.

2.2 Isolation and identification of Microorganism

Sterile swabs were used to aseptically obtain samples and isolate bacteria from sites in the laboratory environment. Samples were obtained aseptically from the surfaces of tables, doors, work benches, fridges, sinks, windows and equipment. Samples obtained were streaked on different eosin methylene blue agar (EMB), Mannitol salt agar (MSA), Macconkey agar and Nutrient agar plates. The inoculated plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Distinct colonies formed were randomly obtained from culture plates. Pure cultures were obtained after subsequent sub culturing of the distinct colonies obtained and maintained on agar slants at 4°C in the refrigerator throughout the duration of study. Pure isolates colonies were identified using previously described standard microbiological techniques (Cheesebrough, 2006) and Matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time of flight (MALDI-TOF-MS) mass spectrometry analysis (Bruker Daltonik GmbH, Bremen, Germany)

RESEARCH ARTICLE

2.3 Preparation of the Disinfectants

A previously described method (Uzoечи et al., 2017) was adopted for the preparation of the disinfectants as shown below.

Original concentration in (%); Ethanol: 99.7%

Phenol: 5%

Other concentrations of ethanol 85% 70% 60% 50% were prepared thus using the formular $R/V \times O$ where R = required concentration, V = required volume of water, O = Original concentration

So if R = 85%, V = 10ml, O = 99.7%

Therefore, $\frac{85\% \times 10\text{ml}}{99.7\%} = 8.50\text{ml}$

Therefore 8.50ml of the disinfectant will be diluted into 1.50ml of sterile water, to get 85% of Disinfectant A. Other concentrations of ethanol and phenol were diluted the same way also to obtain the different concentration used. For each disinfectant, five different test tubes were used and labeled with disinfectant name and concentration

2.4 Antimicrobial susceptibility testing

Five laboratory isolates that had their identities confirmed by MALDI-TOF (matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization time-of-flight) mass spectrometry were used in the susceptibility. The method used by Rollins and Joseph, 2000 and Lages et al., 2008 was used with slight modifications. Different concentrations of the different disinfectants were used for the susceptibility test. 0.1ml of 10^{-2} dilution of each isolate was used to inoculate the pre-prepared Muller Hinton Agar plates and surface plated using a sterile swab sticks. The sterile cork borer {8 mm diameter} was used to bore equidistant holes on the plates. 0.1 mL of the different concentrations of disinfectants was used to fill up the holes. 0.1 mL of sterile distilled water was used as negative control. The experiment was done in triplicates. The petri dishes were then incubated at 37°C for 24hours. The zone of inhibition was obtained using a calibrated ruler and noted, indicating positive results.

3. Results

Table 1 and 2 show the summary of inhibitory activity of the disinfectants on isolates obtained from the laboratory environment

Table 1 Susceptibility results of laboratory isolates to ethanol and phenol

Isolates	Ethanol Concentration %	ZOI(mm)	Phenol Concentration %	ZOI (mm)
2 (<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>)	99.7	12	5	7
	85	15	4	5
	70	14	3	3
	60	7	2	0
	50	9	1	0
4 (<i>Escherichia hermanii</i>)	99.7	8	5	0
	85	11	4	0
	70	0	3	3
	60	4	2	3
	50	4	1	0
10a (<i>Providencia stuartii</i>)	99.7	9	5	13
	85	16	4	14
	70	7	3	13
	60	0	2	13
	50	0	1	0
10e (<i>Leclercia adecarboxylata</i>)	99.7	0	5	14
	85	0	4	14
	70	0	3	0
	60	0	2	0
	50	0	1	0
22 (<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>)	99.7	0	5	15
	85	0	4	15
	70	0	3	13
	60	0	2	11
	50	0	1	0

Key: ZOI- Zone of inhibition in mm

Table 2 Antibacterial activity of the disinfectants on the Laboratory isolates

Organisms	Negative control(sterile distilled water)	Ethanol	Phenol
2(<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>)	0.000±0.000	11.33±1.410*	3.000±1.333*
4(<i>Escherichia hermanii</i>)	0.000±0.000	5.133±1.797*	1.200±0.742*
10a(<i>Providencia stuartii</i>)	0.000±0.000	6.400±2.962*	10.07±2.548*
10e(<i>Leclercia adecarboxylata</i>)	0.000±0.000	0.000±0.000	5.667±3.471*
22(<i>Stenotrophomonas maltophilia</i>)	0.000±0.000	1.000±1.000*	10.73±2.788*

The values above are mean of three replicates n=3. Mean + SEM. Values with superscript * indicates significant difference in relation to the negative control (Sterile distilled water) at P<0.05 while values with no superscript * indicate no significant difference in relation to the negative control (Sterile distilled water)

4. Discussion

Disinfection is an important part of the sanitation procedures, and the activity of disinfectants on microorganisms is of prime importance, as they are agents responsible for different kinds of infections. Results from our study show that the concentration of disinfectants affects their activity. The various active components in the disinfectants could have contributed to the difference in the activity of the disinfectants (Torabi and Zahra, 2025). The disinfectants showed varying activities on the Gram negative bacteria tested in the study. From the results it was noted that not all the

disinfectants inhibited the growth of the test organisms in their concentrated forms. On dilutions of the disinfectants their activities on microorganisms varied (Table 1).

The laboratory isolates were observed to be inhibited mainly at concentrations 60%-85% of ethanol although inhibition of *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Escherichia hermanii* and *Providencia stuartii* was detected at 99.7% of ethanol. This could possibly be as a result of a less rigid cell wall in Gram negative bacteria compared to Gram positive bacteria (Silhavy et al., 2010). However some Gram negative bacteria strains may be more resistant than

RESEARCH ARTICLE

the other. Ethanol was also observed to have inhibitory effects on *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Escherichia hermannii* at a lower concentration of 50% although the inhibitory effect was seen to be minimal. A previous report show ethanol concentrations between 60-95% to be generally effective, with 80-85% considered optimal (Kampf and Kramer, 2004). Higher concentrations were reported to exhibit reduced potency while concentrations below 50% are less effective. Phenol had better inhibitory effects at concentration 3-5% on the isolates obtained from laboratory sites. Statistical data on Table 2 show that phenol had better inhibitory activities on the isolates from laboratory sites compared to ethanol.

Ethanol has been reported to be rapidly bactericidal rather than bacteriostatic against vegetative forms of bacteria both Gram positive and Gram negative but their bactericidal activities reduce when diluted below 60% concentration and the optimum bactericidal concentration are known in the range of 60%- 85% solution in water, volume/volume (Sauerbrei, 2020). The result in this study showed that ethanol at 60-70% gave better effect on some of the test organisms than other ethanol concentrations. Another study on the potentiation of disinfectant efficiency of different dilutions of ethanol, bleach and phenolics against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* showed that as the concentration of ethanol increased, the inhibitory activity decreased (Uzoечи et al., 2017). This correlates with results obtained in this study. According to Weber et al, 1999 and Lobiuc et al., 2023, phenolics are active against bacteria (especially gram positive bacteria). In another previous study showing the antibacterial activity of phenolic compounds against pathogenic bacteria, the results revealed different bacterial species to exhibit different antimicrobial sensitivities towards the tested phenolic compounds. Generally Gram-negative bacteria (*Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*) were observed to have more antimicrobial susceptibility than the Gram-positive bacteria (*Bacillus subtilis*) tested in the study (Tyagi et al., 2015). Owing to its high level of activity, phenol maintains its activity in the presence of organic material as they last long on surfaces unlike ethanol which evaporates easily (Weber et al., 1999).

5. Conclusion

The inhibitory effects of phenol and ethanol at five different concentrations were determined in this study. Conclusively, phenol at a concentration of between 3-5% exhibited notable inhibitory effects against the isolates obtained from the laboratory sites. When these antimicrobial agents are used to disinfect sites suspected to be contaminated with gram positive and gram negative bacteria, use of the disinfectants at appropriate inhibitory concentration will ensure appropriate disinfection processes are carried out.

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